

FIELD APPEARANCE OF *Platygaster diplosisae* RISBEC (HYMENOPTERA: PLATYGASTRIDAE) AND *Aprostocetus procerae* RISBEC (HYMENOPTERA: EULOPHIDAE) AS BIO-CONTROL AGENTS FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF *Orseolia oryzivora* HARRIS AND GAGNÉ (DIPTERA: CECIDOMYIIDAE) IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Orseolia oryzivora Harris and Gagné is an important insect pest of rice in many African countries. Its infestation could result in total crop failure in endemic areas. The use of bio-control agents in the management of the pest is currently attracting the attention of researchers. Two parasitoids; *Platygaster diplosisae* an endoparasitoid and *Aprostocetus procerae* an ectoparasitoid have been found to parasitize a large proportion of *O. oryzivora*. The efficiency of the two parasitoids was compared in the field during 2006/2007, to establish the proportion of the midge parasitized and the amount of that parasitism attribute to each of the parasitoids. Percentage parasitism was established from dissection of collected rice galls. The parasitoids larvae recovered in our studies showed that *P. diplosisae* appeared earlier in the field and was dominant throughout the period of investigation, than *A. procerae* that appeared late and had lower parasitism throughout the period of investigation in both locations. Peak parasitism of the midge occurred between the 2nd and 4th weeks of October for the two parasitoids, years and locations. This study suggests that *P. diplosisae* is a more efficient parasitoid and it's anticipated that it will contribute to the control of *O. oryzivora* in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: *P. diplosisae*, *A. procerae*, bio-control, *O. oryzivora*

INTRODUCTION

African rice gall midge (AFRGM), *Orseolia oryzivora* Harris and Gagné (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) is an important insect pest of rainfed/irrigated lowland rice in Nigeria and many countries in Africa (Williams *et al.*, 1999; Nwilene *et al.*, 2006). It has also been reported in rainfed upland ecology in Burkina Faso (Dakouo *et al.*, 1988). Presently, *O. oryzivora* is the most serious insect pest of lowland rice (Ukwungwu and Misari 1997, Heinrichs and Barrion 2004, Nwilene *et al.*, 2006). *Orseolia oryzivora* attacks rice plant at the vegetative stage. It feeds on the growing primordia, destroying the bud and causing the production of tubular galls (silver shoot or onion leaf) (Heinrichs and Barrion 2004). Feeding on seedlings by *O. oryzivora* larvae lead to profuse tillering and stunting of plants. Any tiller bearing a gall is irreversibly damaged and does not produce new leaves or panicle (Ogah *et al.*, 2010).

Orseolia oryzivora infestations could result in up to 80 % crop losses or in total crop failure especially in endemic areas (Imolehin and Ukwungwu 1992, Ogah *et al.*, 2010).

Several studies have been undertaken to identify appropriate control measures of the pest. The dominant pest control strategy in tropical rice over the past 30 yrs has been the use of insecticide and resistant varieties (Nwilene *et al.*, 2008). Foliar insecticides, though proved to be effective in the control of most insects, have limitation in the management of *O. oryzivora*, probably because of the cryptic nature of its attack. In addition, repeated use of insecticides to control insects have resulted in development of resistance particularly in sub-tropical and tropical countries where farmers tend to apply mixture of chemical insecticides sometimes more than twice a week (Sarfranz and Keddie 2005, Nyasani *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, insecticides are hazardous to the environment and very expensive (Ogah *et al.*, 2009). The uses of resistant varieties have been complicated by the occurrence of *O.*

oryzivora biotypes (WARDA 2000). Consequently, alternative methods of insect control, including bio-control agents are being investigated (Mahar *et al.*, 2004).

Diverse complexes of natural enemies of *O. oryzivora* have been identified in Nigeria and other West African countries that could reduce *O. oryzivora* infestations to tolerable level (Umeh *et al.*, 1991; Ukwungwu and Misari, 1997). Some egg predators have been reported (Williams *et al.*, 2002) which include tiny predatory mites, *Neoseiulus* spp. (Acari: Phytoseiidae), *Cyrtorhinus viridis* Linnavuori (Heteroptera: Miridae), *Conocephalus longipennis* de Haan (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae), *Anaxipha longipennis* Serville (Orthoptera: Gryllidae) and ladybird beetles (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). The most important natural enemies of *O. oryzivora* identified in the fields are the parasitoids. Field surveys of natural enemies of *O. oryzivora* have reported the activities of two promising parasitoids of the *O. oryzivora*; *Platygaster diplosisae* Risbec (Hymenoptera: Platygasteridae), and *Aprostocetus procerae* Risbec (*Tetrastichus pachydiplosisae*) Risbec (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae). *P. diplosisae* Risbec is a koinbiont gregarious egg/larval endoparasitoid and *A. procerae* is a solitary larval/pupal ectoparasitoid (Dakouo *et al.*, 1988, Umeh and Joshi 1992, 1993 and Ogah *et al.*, 2009). Parasitism caused by these two parasitoids could reach as high as 77% of the immature populations of the pest. These potentials could be tapped and used as bio-control agents of *O. oryzivora* (Williams *et al.*, 1999; Ba, 2003, Ogah *et al.*, 2009). *Platygaster oryzae* has been reported to be very effective in the management of the Asian rice gall midge that is similar to the *O. oryzivora* (Hidaka *et al.*, 1988).

Although previous surveys have provided some basic useful information on the potentials of these parasitoids, no empirical experiments have been conducted to determine the effectiveness of these parasitoids on comparative basis under field conditions that approximate commercial agriculture growing conditions.

The objective of the study was therefore to compare the efficiency of these parasitoids as bio-control agents for the management of *O. oryzivora*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

The field experiments were conducted at two locations identified as *O. oryzivora* endemic areas in Nigeria. The two outbreak areas are in different agro ecological zones in Nigeria with different seasonal climatic patterns. All have recorded regular outbreak of *O. oryzivora* since the late 1980s. The two ecological zones were Ogidiga in Southeastern Nigeria, and Edozhigi in North central Nigeria. Ogidiga falls within the forest-savannah transition agro-ecological zone with geographical bearing of latitude 06° 17' N, longitude 08° 04' E, and altitude 104.40 m above sea level. Edozhigi falls within the Guinea Savannah agro ecological zone with geographical bearing of latitude 09° 45' N, longitude 06° 07' E, and altitude 50.57 m above sea level. Their rainfall patterns are bimodal with an average annual rainfall of about 1800-2200 mm and 900-1050 mm per annum for Ogidiga and Edozhigi respectively, distributed between May and October. Their average daily temperature fluctuates between 20 and 35 °C with an annual mean of 26.5°C and 27.4°C respectively. Mean relative humidity were in the ranges of 64 – 83 and 52 – 73 for Ogidiga and Edozhigi respectively. The soils are Utisol and Alfisol and slightly acidic with pH of 4.5 to 4.9 and 5.5 to 6.3 for Ogidiga and Edozhigi respectively.

Field sampling

The study was conducted in farmers' fields at Ogidiga and Edozhigi. The field was also used for experimental work on AfrGM by both the Africa Rice Center (AfricaRice) and the National Cereal Research Institute (NCRI). The area was planted with lowland rice in each location and measured approximately 0.5 ha. Planting was done from May of each farming year. The rice variety grown at Ogidiga was Cisadane – released as FARO 51 in Nigeria. At Edozhigi, ITA 306 (also known as FARO 37) was used. Both varieties are susceptible to the AfrGM. Insecticides were not applied on any of the fields sampled. Sampling for AfrGM infestation and percentage parasitism by both parasitoids were conducted at monthly intervals at both locations from June to December of 2006 and 2007. For each field sampled, 50 plants were randomly selected to assess the intensity of damage due to AfrGM (% tiller infestation) and dissected for % parasitism (parasitized larvae and pupae and parasitoid species present).

Statistical Analysis

An arcsine transformation was carried out on percentage tiller infestation and % parasitism data prior to ANOVA (SAS, 2003). The mean separation was carried out by Tukey's studentized range test. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine the relationship between % tiller infestation, and % parasitism by *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae*.

RESULTS

The impact of *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae* as bio-control agents were based on the percentage AfRGM infestations in the field. The infestations varied significantly among the sampled locations and years (Fig. 1). Generally, AfRGM infestation was less frequent during the initial stages of the survey at both sites but increased with time. Edozhigi in the moist savannah zone had highest percentage infestation recorded in October of each season (Fig.1). The trend was the same at Ogidiga savannah/forest transition zone where infestation increased rapidly from August to October and decreased afterwards.

The field experiments recorded two species of hymenopterous parasitoids parasitizing rice gall midge; *Platygaster diplosisae* and *Aprostocetus procerae*. Dissection of tillers made during the first 6 weeks of galls' appearance showed that at both locations, *P. diplosisae* a gregarious endoparasitoid was the first parasitoid species recorded in the fields sampled, followed by *A. procerae* a solitary larva and pupa ectoparasitoid that appeared 2 weeks later. In the Guinea savanna zone, *P. diplosisae* was the most abundant parasitoid parasitizing AfRGM larvae during the 2006 and 2007 rainy seasons. The % parasitism by *P. diplosisae* was delayed by 2 months after which parasitism increased from late August to October across the years (Fig. 1). In October, when the AfRGM populations peaked the % parasitism by *P. diplosisae* also peaked and dominated the field throughout the 2006 and 2007 rainy seasons. The number of *P. diplosisae* adults recovered from each rice gall dissected varied greatly with a range of 40–67 adults and an average of 53 individuals per rice gall. In the forest zone, percentage parasitism by *P. diplosisae* was much lower than in the Guinea savanna zone. *A. procerae* was a bit scarce at the beginning at both sites, but later on increased with a peak at October during 2006 and 2007 farming seasons respectively Fig. 1.

At Ogidiga the same parasitoid abundance trend was recorded, however percentage parasitism was much lower and delayed till September, then increased very abruptly after that reflecting the late but very rapid buildup of *O. oryzivora* observed there. In October when the *O. oryzivora* populations were on the peak, the parasitoids abundance was also on the peak with *P. diplosisae* dominating the field throughout the period of the experiments

There were no significant differences in % parasitism between the two locations. However, Edozhigi had higher % parasitism during the 2-year study. Beginning from November, populations of AfRGM and both parasitoids were observed to decline slowly. There was a strong positive correlation between tiller infestation and % parasitism by *P. diplosisae* ($r = 0.89$, $P \leq 0.0001$) and *A. procerae* ($r = 0.86$, $P \leq 0.0001$).

DISCUSSION

Parasitism is very important in the biological control of AfRGM (Nacro *et al.*, 1995). Generally, *P. diplosisae* was observed to be more abundant than *A. procerae* in the present study, especially at Edozhigi. *Aprostocetus procerae* appeared later than *P. diplosisae*. Ukwungwu and Joshi (1992a) reported that *P. diplosisae* is the dominant parasitoid species attacking AfRGM in Nigeria. In another study also conducted at Ogidiga, one of our study sites, Umeh and Joshi (1993) similarly recorded *P. diplosisae* as the dominant parasitoid of AfRGM. The dominance of *P. oryzae* has also been reported in India by Joshi and Venugopal (1985), and in other Asian countries where *O. oryzae* is a major pest (Hidaka *et al.*, 1988). In the present study, *P. diplosisae* was the first parasitoid species to establish in the field, and it maintained a higher rate of parasitism than *A. procerae* throughout the season and across both years of the study.

The quicker decline in gall density observed in November as parasitism increased could be attributed to the parasitoids as previously reported by Umeh and Joshi (1993). The gregariousness of *P. diplosisae* and the exploitation of the host early in the season may be advantageous to this species as an effective biological control agent of AfRGM. These findings and those of earlier studies by Dakouo *et al.* (1988) and Ukwungwu and Misari

(1997) suggest that *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae* are the only indigenous parasitoids with high potential for biological control of AfRGM.

CONCLUSION

We thus conclude that *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae* are important parasitoids of African rice gall midge, however, *P. diplosisae* is a more efficient parasitoid and it's anticipated that if conserved to enhance its synchrony with that of the host population may positively contribute towards biological control of AfRGM in lowland rice-based ecosystems in Nigeria and West Africa in general.

Ogidiga 2007

Edozhigi 2006

Edozhigi 2007

Fig. 1: Percent tiller infestation and parasitism by *Platygaster diplosisae* and *Aprostocetus procerae* at Ogidiga and Edozhigi during the 2006 and 2007 rainy seasons.

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